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Technology and Gender
Final Semester Assignment

Gender Citation Gap Reinforced by Digital Technologies?

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1. Presentation of the Semester Assignment

As a master's student focusing on technology and its impact on society and vice versa, a large part of my master's programme is to write a master's thesis. What research topics, authors, and literature we students choose plays an essential role in the quality of our work. Hence the reason I asked myself a question: Could it be that our choices of syllabus and literature we choose to cite are gender-biased, and if so, how? Throughout Technology and Gender course, I have learned to look at society and technology from a gendered perspective, focusing mainly on gender-based differences in status and power (EIGE, 2021). I hope researching the topic of the gender citation gap in this assignment will help me write better future studies. I want to cast light on this subject as the gender biases in our society are increasingly subtle and challenging to see at first sight.

Scientific research receives visibility and impact through citations; hence, some groups may become less visible. Technology, especially search engines, might reinforce this impact. I hope the equal citation of male and female authors in this assignment and my master's thesis will contribute to a more balanced society, regardless of the technology used.

'Technology is neither good nor evil, it is human use that determines its direction' (Hareide, 2020, s. 22).

1.1 Introduction

According to Dion, Summer and Mitchell (2018), scholars receive many benefits when other scholars cite their research. This also influences their publication possibilities, placement of their articles within the journals and overall recognition by popular academic journals. Further on, the overall scholarly career is influenced in the form of higher salaries, career progress and comprehensive academic service. Unfortunately, according to (Dion, Sumner, & Mitchell, 2018) (Maliniak, Powers, & Walter, 2013) (Dworkin, et al., 2020), there is a gender citation gap within many scientific fields. According to others (Budrikis, 2020) (Huang, Gates, Sinatra, & Barabasi, 2020), it is growing. The main concern is that scientific work led by women is less cited compared to comparable work led by men; hence, women's scientific contribution is undervalued and undervalued.

1.2 Topic

In my assignment, I would like to focus on two questions and possible explanations:

- 1) Does the gender citation gap exist, and if so, what are the possible explanations?
- 2) Do the new digital technologies play any role in reinforcing the gender citation gap?

1.3 The Choice of Literature

I chose the literature based on three parameters: First, I chose a field of political science as the starting point as my first master's degree is in political science. I might have been biased here, as this field has recently received much attention. Hence, I might be influenced in my choice of literature by the ranking in Google Scholar and UiA's Online Library when searching for *Gender Citation Gap*. Secondly, I chose the research articles covering both genders and mixed teams of authors as far as I could evaluate their gender from the authors' first names. Gender, in this case, is defined and connected to their first name, typically being assigned to a male or female. Lastly, I chose to focus on Google Scholar, a search engine technology, using algorithms in the ranking of the scientific research and the citation count as a significant variable in defining the ranking position.

2. Gender Citation Gap

Throughout the course Gender and Technology, many articles in the curriculum assessed the topic of who 'owns' knowledge and whether technologies add to the discrepancies in gender equality. The gender citation gap is one of the topics that concerns many researchers as the implications increase the author's visibility and progress in their academic career. It also directly touches on the question of who 'owns' knowledge and how technologies might contribute to gender inequality.

According to Maliniak et al., women are systematically cited less than their male colleagues. On the other hand, the gap declines to some extent once they team up with men in team projects and publish as co-authors of scientific papers. Even after controlling for several variables, such as year of publication, venue of publication, substantive focus, theoretical perspective, methodology, tenure status, and institutional affiliation, the research shows a systematic under-citation of women. Articles written by female authors receive 80% of the citations compared to male-authored articles would receive. They also confirmed that older articles receive more citations than younger articles, even though they see over time a declining tendency. Further on, their findings demonstrate that the co-authorship with mixed teams improves the chances of an article being more cited (Maliniak, Powers, & Walter, 2013). But even after the collaboration and co-authorship, the gender citation gap still persists and does not adjust accordingly as more women enter the field (Dion, Sumner, & Mitchell, 2018).

Acknowledgement and confirmation of findings that the gender citation gap exists are essential as it shows that the problem will not go away with time and with more women in science, even if it might improve over time. The topic of the gender citation gap is important to study as it might be one of the reasons women drop out of scientific careers, adding to the complex problem of a 'leaky pipeline' (Sørensen, Faulkner, & Rommes, 2011, s. 171).

Some possibilities for the existence of the gender citation gap are the number of scientific papers published by men and women, gender-specific patterns such as self-citations, and a lower percentage of women compared to men in the field. In this part, I would like to present some of the possibilities and reasons why the gender citation gap exists and show that it persists even if the general gender gap is diminished and equated.

2.1 Matthew Effect

The Matthew effect is commonly known as an accumulated advantage. In other words: the rich get richer while the poor get poorer. In citation patterns focusing on gender, the Matthew effect applies to male authors being predominantly more cited than female authors. The dominance of male authors explains this effect. Their work is more published in male-dominant fields where men are the prominent authors. The Matthew effect is a process of cumulative advantage where 'celebrity' scientists receive credit for their work independently of their contribution. This 'fame effect' creates inequality in the ways scientists are recognized for their contribution to science. The gender-specific patterns such as self-citations play also a role in this effect; another possible explanation is the affiliation to prestigious institutions and universities or publication in popular peer-review journals (Dion, Sumner, & Mitchell, 2018).

2.2 Matilda Effect

Female contributions have been historically undervalued. This contrasts with the Matthew effect and is called the Matilda effect. The Matilda effect emerges in citations where the work of female scholars is overlooked, or in the case of team research with male and female contributors, the work

is attributed to male scholars (Dion, Sumner, & Mitchell, 2018). For example, I would point out the article by Heather Ford and Judy Wajcman about infrastructure and editing practices on the Wikipedia platform. They evaluated Wikipedia's policies which in summary are based on three principles: neutral point of view, no original research and verifiability. Editors cannot do the original research and must cite only relevant sources outside the encyclopedia sphere to avoid conflict of interest. All that is published on Wikipedia had been already published by external sources. From a historical perspective, this explains why fewer articles about women and their contribution to science are published on Wikipedia. The lack of citations or sources is the main reason for the exclusion of new articles, and the few existing sources are often considered unreliable. These practices reinforce the historical denial of women's contributions to science (Ford & Wajcman, 2017) and reinforce Matilda's effect.

2.3 Self-citations

'When a scholar cites his or her own research ('self-citation'), this act may have a consequential impact on overall citations by both directly and indirectly increasing an author's citation counts' (King, Bergstrom, Correll, Jacquet, & West, 2017).

King et al. refer to the additionally generated citations, which each citation creates (be it a self-citation or citation by other scientists in general). According to Fowler and Aksnes, each self-citation generates 3,65 additional citations from other researchers after ten years and adds to the cumulative advantage. So even if self-citations are subtracted, they have already created additional citations by others (Fowler & Aksnes, 2007). In the research of King et al. across different fields and years, findings show that approximately 1 in 10 citations is a self-citation. Furthermore, the average male author cites his work 56% more often than the average female scientist. Female scientists are more likely not to cite their work at all. This means that women are overrepresented in zero-citations and underrepresented to cite their work at all (King, Bergstrom, Correll, Jacquet, & West, 2017). Explaining these patterns helps clarify that this is not necessarily abnormal over-citations by male authors. A standard way of doing scientific research is to cite own work less than five times. However, this indicates that self-citations impact and make up an essential part of the scientist's work.

2.4 Productivity and Time

According to Huang et al., the gradual increase of women in science also creates gender gaps in scientific productivity and impact. The gender gap in productivity in the 1950s was smaller than in the 2000s. The same applies to gender impact, which switched from slightly more female impact in the 1950s to a 34% gap in favour of male authors. This suggests and supports the work of Dion et al. and Maliniak et al. that achieving gender equality by increasing the number of female scientists is not enough (Huang, Gates, Sinatra, & Barabasi, 2020).

Further on, Huang et al. found that the overall increase of women in academia was accompanied by gender disparities in productivity and time, even though their findings show no difference in the annual productivity for women and men. It is relatively negligible as both female and male authors publish an app. 1.33 papers per year. But what differentiates male scientists from female scientists is their career length. On average, 9% of male scientists and 10.8% of female scientists stop publishing each year. This leads to a 19.5% higher risk for female scientists than male scientists to leave academia, giving male scientists a cumulative advantage (Huang, Gates, Sinatra, & Barabasi, 2020).

The findings of Huang et al. show that the scientific career of male authors compared to female authors is more prolonged, almost by two years. The academic age for male scientists is app. 11 years and for female scientists 9.3 years. This suggests that the total productivity gap is rooted in

career length and the career length is a significant correlate of gender differences in the lives of scientists.

The career length might significantly impact the gender citation gap as a scientist's total productivity is in favour of male scientists, who stay longer in academia and have longer active publishing. On the other hand, this does not consider other forms of an academic career outside of active publishing.

2.5 Scientific Journals

According to Sumpter, the quality of a paper is often based on the impact of a scientific journal it is published in, and known authors and their reputations matter more than the actual quality of the research (Sumpter, 2018).

Research by Brown and Samuel confirms that gender did not play a role in editorial outcomes of four major journals for political science. According to the editors of these journals, the factors which mattered most were:

- 1) A methodological approach- quantitative approach had a higher probability of being published than qualitative
- 2) A rank of the most senior author- the rich get richer syndrome
- 3) Co-authorship (co-authored papers had a higher probability of being published than single-authored papers) (Brown & Samuels, 2018).

Their findings show that women submit fewer articles in general and fewer articles to particular journals. They believe that sociological factors play a significant role: 1) Men publish more over their whole scientific career as their publishing career lasts longer and hence have more possibilities to capture citations. And with more citations comes greater career success. 2) Collaboration predicts publishing success. Collaboration with women in mixed teams might be neglected or even avoided as women are less likely to be cited, and their presence might create a 'disadvantage' for a published article. If they do collaborate, the gender citation gap in the co-authored paper still remains. 3) Lastly, a journal's social perception and 'image' is an essential factor in female scholars' decision to submit a paper or have a chance to be published. Hence editors have the power to address this issue by recognizing it and making scholars aware of it. Amanda Murdie suggests that editors should include the findings about the persistence of the gender citation gap in the journal's submission guidelines and help eradicate this gap (Murdie, 2018).

3. The Impact of Digital Databases and Search Algorithms on Gender Citation Gap

According to King et al., some databases separate citation count and self-citation information. Others, such as Google Scholar, do not. Adding to the cumulative advantage of self-citations, another cumulative advantage seems to build up – the algorithms. Adding to the gender citation gap, citation counts determine the ranking of an article and thus reinforcing the Matthew effect.

3.1 The Role of Google Scholar

According to Beel and Gipp, Google Scholar is one of the major academic search engines with an unknown ranking algorithm. They tried to reverse-engineer this algorithm to find out if there is any correlation between the article citation count and its ranking on Google Scholar. Their findings confirm that the citation count is the primary factor in Google Scholar's algorithm ranking. The articles with a 'celebrity' status (the Matthew effect) appear higher in ranking. They are placed on the first search page and, consequently, are cited, getting an additional accumulative advantage (around 90% of clicks were performed on the first page) (Beel & Gipp, 2009).

Although Google Scholars heavily influences what research appears and hence what gets the most attention from researchers, there is little known about how the algorithm works. According to Google Scholar, the algorithm works precisely as researchers themselves would perform a search. And suppose this is the case, and we know the research is already based on implicit biases; as this paper shows, in that case, the technology might mirror and even amplify the gender citation gap. The research of Beel and Gipp confirms that the citation count significantly impacts the article's ranking. Although it is probably not the only factor, their research shows an almost perfect relationship between ranking and article citation count. They further assume that the other factors might have little or no impact on the ranking.

Prof. Sumpter at Uppsala University, Sweden, calls the ranking on Google Scholar a popularity contest. He compares becoming a top Youtuber with a high number of likes to become a top scientist on top of the first page of Google Scholar. Based on the search term, the order the articles are presented is according to the number of citations and references in other articles. This helps assess the importance of an article in the field and help a researcher show how other researchers think. But there are side effects. Google Scholar is a powerful tool, helping to save time and effort, showing researchers the most cited research in the first place. The popularity of an article is captured by a mathematical power law, where one quantity varies as the power of another. This leads to vast inequality. According to Sumpter, in 2008, 73% of all articles on Google Scholar were cited once or less. On the other side, 1 of 100 000 articles was cited 2000 times or more. There are many articles that no one ever reads and very few very popular articles that many read (Sumpter, 2018).

4. Conclusion

Even though the greater diversity in the scientific field improves the recognition of female scholars, the gender citation gap remains nonetheless.

'The proportion of women in a subfield or discipline is clearly associated with gendered citation practices for all scholars working in those fields. While greater gender representation in an academic field improves attribution of ideas to work by women scholars, the citation gender gap persists, providing evidence in favor of the 'Matilda effect' (Dion, Sumner, & Mitchell, 2018).

There are some ideas on what can be done to address the Matilda effect. The main reason this citation gap exists in the first place is the lack of diversity in the field. Secondly, there should be rules applied to scientific papers to include female authors or clarify why there is a lack of such works based on a percentage of works by female scholars in the field. Another reason is the methodological focus, where quantitative research is overrepresented over qualitative research, excluding female scientists and scientists with minority backgrounds, which tend to qualitative research. Recognizing the importance of qualitative research is another way to go. Highly ranked and internationally recognized journals should have publication policies to include research presented by female and minority scholars to present the broad spectrum of scientific research.

According to King et al., there is a difference in the perception of male and female self-citations. Female authors need to evaluate their abilities more, and the tendency to 'punish' them for self-citations and self-promoting as less competent needs to improve in academia (King, Bergstrom, Correll, Jacquet, & West, 2017). As citations follow the pattern that recognizes scientific papers and authors which are already well-cited, self-citations increase the cumulative advantage.

Regarding algorithms based on citation count, the most important is how citations are interpreted and used. On one side, algorithms have a lot of positive effects, where work is shared more rapidly and widely, and they save researchers a lot of time. But they alone should not determine how we see the world. Academia must challenge tech companies on how they transform the academic world into algorithms. When creating algorithms, one must be aware of implicit biases, historical denial of women's and minorities' contribution to science, the Matthew and Matilda effect, and social patterns of self-citations. That way, in cooperation with the scientific community, they can produce much better search engines with multiple sorting algorithms and search choices. They can build transparent algorithms, which we know precisely how they work, and we can be aware of potential biases. Hopefully, the creation of algorithms with inbuilt values cherishing equality and quality of scientific work will be a major concern rather than a quantitative evaluation of scientists.

To end my semester assignment, I would like to conclude positively. I agree with Dion et al. (2018) that the gender citation gap does not exist and persists due to deliberative discrimination. I neither believe that citation counts are objective measures of the author's quality. I think the gender citation gap exists due to subtle mechanisms and social patterns such as implicit biases, self-citation mechanisms, and how the search engines are built to highlight one article over another. A lack of senior female scholars and overall gender inequality in the field adds to the problem. I believe many scholars and students are unaware of the gender citation gap. Awareness is the key to addressing this issue from multiple angles, adding to understanding the problem. Creating the overall awareness and space for discussion, with specific citation guidelines for scholars and students, will consequently lead to eradicating this gap.

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